

· THE UNITED KINGDOM ·

NATIONAL REMOTE SENSING CENTRE

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REMOTE SENSING

"Remote sensing is the science of acquiring and interpreting information about the Earth's environment from measurements made without physical contact"

Man's initial plans for spaceflight were to escape from the Earth, with dreams of travel to other planets. But the astronauts of the 1960s could not resist 'looking down' at the view of their own fragile world and we earth-bound individuals marvelled at the TV transmissions and the photographs they collected – remote sensing from space was born. During the following decade a series of unmanned satellites was launched with a variety of experimental remote sensing instruments designed to record details of the land surface, the oceans and the atmosphere. The images generated from the data they transmitted to ground stations around the world have provided a wealth of unique information. Now satellite data is becoming an everyday part of our lives – improvements in weather forecasting and its explanation to the general public is an obvious and frequently quoted example. In the near future, with the next generation of satellites and developments in the analysis of the data, many more operational uses of remote sensing will emerge and the 'eyes in the sky' will play an active part in the monitoring and protection of our environment.

This brochure outlines the role of the National Remote Sensing Centre at RAE Farnborough and its major activities. Although primarily aimed at a UK audience, it is hoped that this information will also be of interest to overseas readers. Remote sensing technology itself is only briefly touched upon and the brochure concentrates primarily on the facilities and services the NRSC provides to its customers and users.

An image of the Earth taken by the GOES-E satellite from a height of almost 36,000 km. GOES-E forms part of a global network of meteorological satellites, acquiring data every 30 minutes. An important role of weather satellites is their ability to provide timely data on the movement of severe weather disturbances. This particular image shows Hurricane David, the most intense and destructive of the 1979 season.

THE NRSC – an introduction

The NRSC was established in 1980 to promote the use of satellite imagery in the UK. The Centre operates within Space Department at the Royal Aerospace Establishment (RAE) Farnborough, but is located outside the perimeter of the RAE, to permit easier access for the user community.

The policies and funding of the NRSC are determined by the British National Space Centre (BNSC) and the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI), in close collaboration with the Ministry of Defence.

Over the years the NRSC has helped to establish a number of Regional Centres. These are at Silsoe College in Bedfordshire, the Macaulay Land Use Research Institute in Aberdeen, the Ordnance Survey of Northern Ireland in Belfast and the University College of Wales in Swansea.

The NRSC is mainly interested in satellite imagery of the UK. However, the Centre will assist its customers and users to obtain imagery or information for any part of the world.

The NRSC aims to:

- supply remote sensing data and imagery
- assist British industry in its remote sensing activities
- act as a focal point for the development of remote sensing techniques and their application
- provide education and training facilities in remote sensing

ANTARCTIC MOSAIC

This unique view of Antarctica is the result of a joint project between the NRSC and NOAA of the United States. It was produced using visible and infra-red data from the AVHRR sensor onboard NOAA's polar orbiting satellites and is essentially a 'patchwork' of some 23 separate scenes.

SATELLITES AND DATA RECEPTION

In general terms remote sensing satellites record information about the Earth's environment – the atmosphere, the land and the oceans, although some sensors designed for one area are finding application in another.

The atmosphere

Sensors for meteorological applications record data of relatively large areas at a regional level of detail and with a frequent repeat cycle. Two types of satellites are used operationally – a network in geostationary orbit almost 36,000 km above the Equator, providing a broad view of global weather patterns every thirty minutes (e.g. **Meteosat**, **GOES**) and the lower polar orbiting **NOAA satellites**, collecting a wide range of more detailed environmental data.

The land

Launched in 1972 **Landsat 1** was the first satellite designed specifically to collect data about the Earth's surface and resources, and its success demonstrated the potential of remote sensing from space. Subsequent launches have given a near-continuous service, with many users coming to rely on the data. Applications have been found in many fields including geology, mineral and petroleum exploration, forestry and agriculture, hydrology, land use and land cover evaluation, mapping environmental changes, resources inventories and pollution monitoring.

Further important advances occurred with the launch of **SPOT-1** in 1986 and the introduction of a high resolution sensor based on linear arrays, which can be pointed to obtain stereoscopic images or increase the frequency of coverage of a particular area.

The oceans

To adequately monitor geophysical parameters of the ocean, sensors must be enhanced for the unique features of this environment.

Two experimental satellites were launched in 1978 – the **Nimbus-7 Coastal Zone Colour Scanner** aimed to establish optimum characteristics for mapping and measuring suspended materials and other phenomena in coastal waters, while **Seasat** provided the first opportunity to acquire, receive, process and analyse data from a spaceborne Synthetic Aperture Radar. Although short-lived, Seasat acquired a wealth of unique information, which continues to play an important role in the preparation for the next generation of microwave satellites, such as **ERS-1**.

ERS-1 will be the forerunner of a series of satellites launched in the 1990s to monitor ocean and ice environments, with the capability of measuring various parameters, such as wind speed and direction, wave spectra, wave height, etc., and acquiring all-weather high resolution imagery over the ocean, coastal regions and land.

Washington D.C. as seen from the Multispectral Scanner System (MSS) onboard Landsat 4. The main features are Arlington Cemetery, the Pentagon, the White House, the city's National Airport, the Potomac River and the Anacostia River which branches to the east. ▲

A simulated natural colour mosaic of the British Isles using 52 Landsat MSS images. ▼

The role of the NRSC in supplying data and imagery

As part of its service, the NRSC assists users with the procurement of remote sensing data from various agencies, including:

EARTHNET

The NRSC is the UK National Point of Contact with Earthnet, which distributes data from Seasat, Nimbus-7 Coastal Zone Colour Scanner, Heat Capacity Mapping Mission, Metric Camera, MOS-1 and various meteorological satellites.

SPOT IMAGE

Since June 1986 the NRSC has been licensed to distribute SPOT data in the UK.

EURIMAGE

The NRSC is an authorised distributor for EURIMAGE, which is responsible for Landsat data in Europe.

Landsat data from other areas of the world are purchased either from EOSAT in the USA or directly from the ground station operators.

The NRSC also has an extensive archive of satellite data, stored in a central facility maintained by RAE Space Department, which includes:

- all good quality Landsat imagery of the UK, plus a large archive of overseas scenes
- all good quality multispectral and panchromatic SPOT imagery of the UK
- data from NASA's experimental and Shuttle missions
- Seasat SAR and Low Bit Rate data
- a two-week rolling archive of NOAA data, which is maintained by RAE Lasham. Selected scenes are transferred to a permanent archive with sample data from Meteosat and other geostationary satellites

A Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM) image of Gibraltar and northern Morocco. The docks and jetties of Gibraltar's harbour are clearly visible.

NRSC USER SERVICES

– customer support

The NRSC provides a comprehensive range of services, facilities and products to cover the needs of all remote sensing data users. The principal customer support services include:

ENQUIRY SERVICE

The NRSC handles all types of remote sensing enquiry, whether of a technical, applications or general nature. If a query cannot be answered in-house the Centre has numerous national and international contacts to help solve the problem.

DATA SEARCHES

Every effort is taken to locate information and identify the availability and quality of imagery to meet specific requests. Facsimile and data retrieval links exist between the NRSC and international organisations to speed these data searches.

DEMONSTRATIONS AND LECTURES

The use of image analysis systems are demonstrated, either in general terms or for a specific application of satellite data, e.g. geology, water resources, etc.. Group visits, particularly for educational purposes, are welcomed. Also, from time-to-time, open days or specific applications oriented workshops are organised.

DOCUMENTATION SERVICE

An important element of the NRSC's work involves the preparation and distribution of a number of promotional and technical documents:

- newsletters
- brochures
- fact sheets
- introductory guide
- user guides
- working papers
- catalogues
- reports and pamphlets

EDUCATIONAL PRODUCTS

A range of products to provide both an introduction to remote sensing and more advanced information is continually under development aimed at schools, colleges and higher educational establishments. This series includes videos, slide sets, posters, wallcharts, teaching packs and publications.

NRSC LIBRARY AND BROWSE FACILITIES

The library at the NRSC houses an up-to-date collection of remote sensing books, journals, reports and documents together with a collection of videos and 35 mm slides.

One of the NRSC's most important user services is its image 'browse facility', which is used for customer searches or by visitors undertaking their own evaluations of available satellite data. This consists of:

- a quick look archive (proof prints) of all Landsat data acquired of the UK and Ireland
- colour prints of all photographic negatives generated from the Space Department archive
- microfiche catalogues for several satellite and Shuttle missions
- worldwide coverage maps and information logs for Landsat, SPOT and other programmes

IMAGE ANALYSIS

The NRSC has a suite of dedicated image analysis systems, which are available to outside users for hire by the hour. These GEMS systems are very easy to use and have been designed to handle current and future satellite data, airborne scanner imagery and digitised aerial photographs and maps. After a short period of tuition a new user will be able to manipulate, enhance and classify images and will rapidly gain confidence using the system. No knowledge of computer programming or special typing skills are necessary, and an experienced operator is on-hand to help if required. Low-cost hard copy output from the system is generated using off-screen photography or ink-jet plotters.

For higher quality products, a photographic master can be prepared using laser filmwriters, within Space Department's photographic facility.

A micro-based image processing system is available at the Centre for demonstration purposes and is used in visits to schools and colleges around the country.

In addition to these interactive systems, the NRSC has access to a range of off-line programs for routine processing and such special activities as geometric correction to specific projections, combining images and maps and mosaicing images.

Area in central Tunisia showing complex folding and over-thrusting of Mesozoic sediments in a semi-arid region at the eastern end of the Atlas Fold Belt. The image below is a three-band colour composite (4, 5, 7 – R, G, B) and displays only very limited spectral discrimination of rock units and superficial deposits due to a high degree of inter-band correlation.

The image to the right is a band ratio image with band 3/1 in red, 5/4 in green and 5/7 in blue. Ratio images are widely used in geological remote sensing to enhance lithological discrimination and to improve geological interpretation. The 3/1 and 5/4 ratios are sensitive to iron oxides while the 5/7 ratio is used to enhance carbonate rocks and to highlight areas of increased clay content. In this example, topographic expression, which is flattened by ratioing, has been preserved by controlling image intensity with the first principal component of the data.

PHOTOGRAPHIC SERVICES

The NRSC is able to offer a wide range of photographic products and associated services from Space Department's photographic facility. This is a purpose-built and comprehensively equipped laboratory, with staff specifically trained in the preparation of satellite image products. Its high technical standards and flexibility are well renowned and rigorous quality controls are maintained.

Most satellite data is archived in digital form on computer compatible tape. The process to transfer the data to a photographic master is known as film writing. To meet the exacting technical requirements demanded in the preparation of high quality products, a direct colour laser filmwriter has been developed especially for Space Department. With this sophisticated equipment the digital data is transferred, in one pass, to a colour master. The precision mechanics and laser technology achieve very high colour density and registration accuracies.

Photographic products can be generated from any scene within the data archives, as specially processed data or from data tapes supplied by users. A comprehensive range of standard products (prints, film negatives, and transparencies) can be prepared from black and white or colour masters. Prints are available at various sizes and can be matched to either image scale or print measurement requirements. In addition, non-standard items can be prepared to meet user's requirements.

A Landsat 5 Thematic Mapper (TM) image stretching from south of Tel Aviv to the edges of Haifa in the north. Of interest is the dramatic 'boundary' between the irrigated land near the coast and the more inhospitable terrain to the east.

▼ *The 10 m resolution of the SPOT panchromatic instrument reveals an enormous amount of detail in this image of Southampton (© CNES 1987)*

An MSS image showing the island of Bahrain in the Arabian Gulf. The light blue tones provide an indication of shallow water zones. ▲

A Landsat 4 TM image of the Bay of Naples, including the city of Naples, the spectacular volcanic cone of Vesuvius and the islands of Ischia and Capri. ▼

A Landsat 5 MSS image of the Nile Delta. ▲ The river may be seen to the left of the image whilst the Suez Canal is to the right. Of particular interest are the distinctive circular patterns created by irrigation schemes.

APPLICATIONS DEVELOPMENT

Remote sensing is a highly effective method of conducting resource surveys, monitoring the natural environment and mapping. Where appropriate, general and detailed investigations can be made quickly, accurately and at a fraction of the cost of conventional ground methods.

As part of its programme to stimulate and promote the use of remote sensing in the UK, the NRSC has a permanent team of experienced applications scientists, who provide customers with assistance and advice on the uses of the various types of satellite data.

The main aims of the consultancy service are to:

- provide new users with training and scientific support
- assist users on the GEMS digital image processing systems and provide advice on a variety of applications
- collaborate with users in developing new applications of the satellite data
- develop operational applications of satellite remote sensing

Each year a number of projects are undertaken, some in collaboration with users, across the wide spectrum of remote sensing applications.

COMMERCIAL APPLICATIONS OF REMOTE SENSING: A CASE STUDY

With the ever increasing use of offshore waters, we need to expand our knowledge of the physical processes that occur in this complex environment. Sea surface temperatures derived from satellite imagery, such as this NOAA AVHRR image of part of the North Sea, can be used to map thermal gradients between different water masses. The upwelling waters at these sites are often nutrient rich, concentrating large populations of marine life, and are, therefore, of great commercial interest to the fishing industry.

Similarly, this satellite imagery can provide valuable information to the offshore construction industry and decision makers involved in waste disposal, where thermal data can be related to sea surface currents.

THE FUTURE

The next decade will see the launch of satellites with improved sensor payloads, in particular in the field of microwave sensing. The first such satellite will be Europe's ERS-1 and the UK is making a major commitment to this programme through the provision of a processing and archiving facility – the Earth Observation Data Centre, based at RAE Farnborough.

Further into the future the Space Station and its associated polar platforms will offer many exciting opportunities for remote sensing.

To complement these developments, advances in image processing techniques and the integration of satellite imagery and digital maps will enable users to extract more accurate information from the data in an increasingly cost-effective manner.

A structural model of the ERS-1 satellite (Courtesy of ESA).

A Seasat SAR image of an area south of Stranraer on the west coast of Scotland. The UK ERS-1 receiving station will be built in this area at West Freugh.

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Cover

A Landsat 5 TM image of the south coast of England, stretching from Cornwall in the west to Dorset in the east. Notable features include the city of Plymouth, Dartmoor, Chesil Beach and Portland Bill, Poole Harbour and the sandy beaches of Bournemouth.

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